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DO PERINATAL RISK FACTORS INFLUENCE THE SEVERITY OF INFLAMMATORY RESPONSE IN NEONATAL SEPSIS?

Abstract.

Objective. The objective of this study was to analyse data pertaining to anamnesis and perinatal risk factors in order to investigate the relationship between the course of neonatal sepsis and the severity of the inflammatory response in newborns. Through a scientific analysis of these factors, the aim was to gain insights into the underlying mechanisms that influence the progression and outcomes of neonatal sepsis, thereby contributing to a deeper understanding of this critical condition in newborn infants.

Materials and methods. 56 medical records of newborns receiving treatment in the neonatal intensive care unit were analysed. Depending on the severity of the inflammatory response, two observation groups were formed. The first clinical group included 25 patients with neonatal sepsis with a serum level of C-reactive protein <20 mg/l. The second group included 31 newborns with sepsis, where the blood CRP levels were over 20 mg/l. The serum presepsin levels in both groups were also over 300 pg/ml.

Results. After analysing the data, it was discovered that the medical history of pregnancy and childbirth, as well as perinatal risk factors, do not impact the severity of the body's inflammatory response in early and late sepsis. Patients with low levels of C-reactive protein in neonatal sepsis are more likely to experience complications such as placental abruption, cesarean section delivery, low Apgar scores at 5 minutes, and a higher need for initial resuscitation. They also have an increased risk of intolerance to food requiring total parenteral nutrition. Babies born with high levels of C-reactive protein are more likely to be born prematurely before 32 weeks, show more severe signs of breathing problems, need more surfactant medication, respiratory support with n-CPAP therapy and mechanical ventilation, are at risk of getting too cold, and may start eating solid food later than normal.

Conclusions. The findings of the study showed that in cases of neonatal sepsis, there is a diverse group of patients with varying levels of inflammation. This group may exhibit characteristics of "severe" sepsis and require personalised clinical and diagnostic interventions.

Keywords: newborns, sepsis, risk factors, medical history, C-reactive protein, procalcitonin.

Introduction. Generalised infectious-inflammatory diseases in newborns represent a pressing medical and social issue in neonatology [1]. The advent of modern perinatal technologies and advancements in diagnostic and therapeutic approaches have contributed, on one hand, to a decline in infant mortality rates. However, they have also led to a rise in the incidence of neonatal sepsis, particularly among premature infants with low or extremely low birth weights [2]. Addressing the challenge of combating sepsis remains paramount in neonatology, especially concerning patients receiving care in neonatal intensive care units [3]. This challenge is exacerbated by the fact that early clinical signs of infectious pathology are often subtle, poorly defined, and nonspecific. They may be attributed to non-infectious causes such as respiratory distress syndrome in newborns, environmental-induced hypothermia, apnea in premature infants, and various other clinical manifestations [4].

The insufficient informativeness of clinical and anamnestic data in detecting neonatal infection has prompted the search for laboratory markers with high diagnostic significance as a potential means to verify diagnoses, predict organ dysfunction development, and assess treatment effectiveness. Recent scientific studies

indicate promise in utilizing the level of presepsin in serum blood to enhance diagnosis, predict neonatal sepsis severity, and monitor therapy.

In light of the above, this study aimed to explore the medical history and perinatal risk factors influencing the course of neonatal sepsis based on the intensity of the inflammatory response in newborns.

Materials and Methods: A retrospective analysis was conducted on 56 medical records of newborns treated in the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU) of the Chernivtsi Regional Children's Clinical Hospital. The study focused on investigating the impact of anamnestic features and risk factors on the severity of the inflammatory response in neonatal sepsis.

Inclusion criteria comprised meeting diagnostic criteria for sepsis, neonatal age, serum procalcitonin level > 300 pg/ml, and parental consent for participation. Exclusion criteria included congenital developmental defects, inability to conduct a comprehensive examination, presence of non-infectious pathology mimicking sepsis, age older than 28 days, and lack of parental consent.

Two observation groups were formed based on the severity of the inflammatory response. Group I included 25 patients with neonatal sepsis and serum C-reactive protein levels <20 mg/l, while Group II

comprised 31 newborns with sepsis and serum CRP levels >20 mg/l.

During the manifestation of clinical signs of sepsis, the distribution among groups was even. Thus,

the proportion of infants with early neonatal sepsis was 40.0% in both groups of observations. A comparative characterization of the observation groups based on the main clinical signs is shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Characteristics of the observation groups

Clinic groups	Number of patients	Place of residence (city)	Gender (boys)	Satisfactory social status	Registered marriage
I group	25	80.0%	52.0%	75.0%	76.1%
II group	31	57.1%	62.8%	80.0%	87.8%
	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND

ND - no difference

Thus, the main clinical characteristics of the comparison group were compared.

The diagnosis and treatment of neonatal sepsis followed the recommendations of leading neonatologists in Ukraine [9], in line with international guidelines [2, 10, 11]. The study was conducted retrospectively using parallel groups selected through simple random sampling.

Immunological assays were performed in the laboratory of the Chernivtsi Regional Children's Clinical Hospital using the enzyme immunoassay method on the "StatFax 303/ Plus" apparatus (USA). This included measuring serum C-reactive protein levels (mg/L) using "CRP IFA - BEST highly sensitive" reagents and serum procalcitonin levels (HumansCD14, ng/ml) using the reagent: HycultBiotechNK 320, Netherlands.

The obtained research data were analysed using the computer software package "Statistica 8.0" by StatSoft and ExcelXP for Windows on a personal computer. Both parametric and non-parametric calculation methods were employed, along with descriptive and correlative analyses. The accuracy of the null hypothesis was assessed considering the significance levels "P" (by Student) and "Pê" (Fisher's angular transformation method). Additionally, from a clinical epidemiology perspective, the relative risk (RR) and odds ratio (OR) of event development were calculated, accompanied by their 95% confidence intervals (95% CI).

The study was conducted in accordance with the basic provisions of bioethics set out in the ICH GCP and the Declaration of Helsinki on Research and the recommendations of the Committee on Bioethics at the Presidium of the Academy of Medical Sciences of Ukraine (2002). Informed parental consent was obtained for the study.

Research results. Analysing the socioeconomic factors potentially contributing to infant sepsis, it was observed that the majority of children in both study groups were born to parents with satisfactory social status and in legally recognized marriages. There were no significant differences in parental age distribution. For instance, the percentage of infants born to mothers under 30 years old in the first clinical group was 78.2%, compared to 65.5% in the second clinical group ($P>0.05$). Similarly, the percentage of fathers under 30 in the comparison groups was 54.5% and 62.5%, respectively ($P>0.05$).

Given that premature birth is a risk factor for neonatal sepsis, we examined the relationship between gestational age and the development of generalized infectious-inflammatory processes. While the proportion of full-term infants with neonatal sepsis in the first clinical group was 16.0%, compared to 11.3% in the comparison group ($p>0.05$), there were no significant differences in the frequency of preterm births. However, among patients in the second clinical group, predominantly very preterm infants born before 32 weeks of gestation accounted for 68.5%, compared to 48.0% in infants of the first group (OR-2.4 (95% CI 1.3-4.2); RR 1.6 (95% CI 1.2-2.0); AR (0.21)). The percentage of infants born before 28 weeks of gestation in the observation groups was 31.4% and 20.0%, respectively ($p>0.05$). Infants in this cohort are known to have immature immune system mechanisms, increasing their susceptibility to bacterial infections. Nonetheless, the risk of preterm birth before 32 weeks of gestation was associated with a high level of C-reactive protein.

More than half of the children (60.0%) in the first observation group were born from the first pregnancy, and every third child (34.3%) in the second clinical group ($P<0.05$). Mostly, the children were born in the head presentation (68.0% and 68.5% of cases, respectively) ($P>0.05$). Half of the infants (52.0%) in the first clinical group were born by cesarean section, while in the second clinical group, this indicator was 40.0% ($P>0.05$). One in five women (20%) in the comparison group underwent cesarean section due to placental abruption, compared to 8.6% ($P>0.05$) of cases in the comparison group mothers. Therefore, cesarean section increased the chances of low levels of C-reactive protein in serum in the presence of sepsis: OR - 2.9 (CI 95% 1.2-6.9); RR - 1.6 (CI 95% 1.0-3.3); AR (0.25).

The indications of fetal distress at birth, which are one of the leading factors in the development of neonatal depression and asphyxia, were equally common in both groups of surveyed infants, with a proportion of 68.0% and 60.0% ($P>0.05$) cases respectively. The consequences of acute hypoxia and the extent of its impact, especially in preterm infants with extracerebral pathology, determine the process of their further postnatal adaptation, as a low Apgar score (1-3 points) at 1 minute of extrauterine life was observed in 16.0% of children in group I and in 20.6% ($P>0.05$) of children in group II. At 5 minutes of life, the persistence of a low Apgar score, which is an

indicator of unfavorable prognosis for the course of the disease, was diagnosed in 16.0% and 11.6% ($P>0.05$) of infants in both observation groups, respectively. The birth of infants in severe asphyxia required full primary resuscitation in 14 (56.0%) newborns in clinical group I and 11 (34.3%, $P<0.05$) children in clinical group II OR - 2.5 (CI 95% 1.4-4.4); RR - 1.6 (CI 95% 1.0-2.2); AR (0.22).

At the same time, in cases of moderate asphyxia with an Apgar score of 4-7 at 1 minute of life, 84.0% of infants in the first clinical group and 73.5% ($P>0.05$) of newborns in the second clinical group were born. Maintenance of Apgar scores of 4-7 at 5 minutes of life was noted in 73.5% of cases in patients of the first clinical group and 62.0% ($P>0.05$) of children in the comparison group, which required initial assistance to stabilize their condition in the delivery room.

Hence, the combination of what are commonly termed as "underlying" conditions, frequently diagnosed in premature infants, along with immature immune defense mechanisms, heightens the risk of disturbances in adaptation mechanisms during the neonatal period. Infants with low C-reactive protein production exhibited lower Apgar scores at 5 minutes, a higher likelihood of requiring primary resuscitation assistance, and challenges in food tolerance, often necessitating total parenteral nutrition. Conversely, newborns with elevated levels of C-reactive protein demonstrated better adaptation processes, correlating with a reduced risk of a low Apgar score (within 1-3 points): with an absolute risk reduction of 45.6% and a relative risk reduction of 13.6%.

The trend towards an increasing number of low birth weight infants resulted in the administration of

surfactant drugs in 51.5% of cases in the second patient group, compared to 28.0% in infants of the first clinical group. Despite this, there were no statistically significant differences in the assessment of the severity of respiratory disorders according to the Downes scale (OR-2.7 (95% CI 1.5-4.9); RR 1.6 (95% CI 1.1-2.3); AR (0.24)). Moderate respiratory distress, with a score of 4-6 points, was present in 71.4% of newborns in the first clinical group and 69.3% in the second group ($p>0.05$). Notably, respiratory support using nCPAP therapy was required by 28.0% of infants in the first group and 47.1% of patients in the second group ($p<0.05$) (OR-2.3 (95% CI 1.3-4.1); RR 1.15 (95% CI 1.01-2.1); AR (0.20)). Additionally, lung ventilation was performed in 31.4% of children in the first clinical group compared to 56.0% in the comparison group ($p>0.05$). However, there were no significant differences in the frequency and severity of respiratory disorders between the patients in both groups. These findings suggest that more pronounced indicators of inflammatory response in neonatal sepsis are linked to more severe respiratory disorders, highlighting the potential of determining procalcitonin levels in serum for enhancing diagnosis and predicting the severity of neonatal sepsis.

When analysing the medical history data, it was noted that pregnancy and childbirth had complicated characteristics in mothers from both observation groups. Therefore, the study focused on the impact of the most important perinatal infectious factors on the course of the disease in infants. A comparative analysis of the medical history indicators of pregnancy and childbirth in mothers of the observation groups is presented in Table 2.

Table 2

Indicators of obstetric and perinatal history of newborns in clinical comparison groups (in %)

Indicator	I group	II group	P
Indications of infertility in the history	8,0	8,6	$>0,05$
Fetoplacental insufficiency	24,0	20,0	$>0,05$
History of anaemia during pregnancy	32,0	31,4	$>0,05$
IVF frequency	8,0	5,7	$>0,05$
Presence of bacteriuria in the mother at any stage of gestation	4,0	14,2	$>0,05$
The duration of membrane rupture is more than 18 hours	20,0	25,7	$>0,05$
Signs of chorioamnionitis	16,0	11,4	$>0,05$
Signs of colpitis	8,0	11,4	$>0,05$
Signs of pyelonephritis	4,0	5,7	$>0,05$
Body temperature in labour over 38.00C	8,3	9,0	$>0,05$

The presence of bacteriuria in the mother at any gestational age, rupture of fetal membranes lasting over 18 hours, signs of chorioamnionitis, colitis, pyelonephritis, and body temperature during labor above 38.00°C are considered significant risk factors for early neonatal sepsis. These factors were equally prevalent in both observation groups and did not show statistical significance. However, correlation analysis revealed a positive association between the level of presepsin and the presence of maternal infectious diseases during pregnancy ($r=0.30$).

Additionally, the use of antibiotic therapy, including third-generation cephalosporins, was more

common among mothers in the second clinical group, accounting for 22.8% compared to 12.0% ($p>0.05$) in the first group. Notably, there were no significant differences between the comparison groups regarding other risk factors for late neonatal sepsis [14], such as the need for resuscitative measures in the delivery room, invasive procedures, lack of "skin-to-skin" contact with the mother, use of parenteral nutrition, and late initiation of enteral feeding. The primary indicators of risk factors for late neonatal sepsis are outlined in Table 3.

Clinical indicators of risk factors for late neonatal sepsis (in%)

Indicator	I group	II group	P
Resuscitation measures	72,0	68,6	>0,05
Invasive procedures	80,0	80,0	>0,05
Lack of contact with mother and father	76,0	77,1	>0,05
Parenteral nutrition	68,0	60,0	>0,05
Late start of enteral feeding	4,0	8,6	>0,05
Hypothermia	4,0	8,6	>0,05
Use of reserve antibiotics	8,0	2,9	>0,05
Long-term hospitalisation	88,0	80,0	>0,05

At the same time, children in the II clinical group were more likely to show a predisposition to hypothermia and indications of a late onset of enteral feeding without statistical significance. Research on correlation relationships showed a probable link between the level of presepsin and a later onset of enteral feeding in infants with sepsis ($r=0.49$). Thus, the obtained data indicate the lack of influence of anamnestic data on the severity of inflammatory response indicators in the development of neonatal sepsis, except for indications of a history of infectious disease in the mother during pregnancy.

Conclusions:

1. The anamnestic data concerning the pregnancy and delivery process, along with perinatal risk factors for the development of early and late sepsis, are not correlated with the severity of inflammatory response markers in the body. Nevertheless, individuals with low levels of C-reactive protein during neonatal sepsis are more likely to experience placental abruption, resulting in an increased requirement for primary resuscitation at birth.

2. In infants exhibiting low levels of C-reactive protein, the progression of neonatal sepsis correlated with a diminished Apgar score at 5 minutes and an elevated likelihood of requiring initial resuscitation. Conversely, newborns with elevated levels of C-reactive protein demonstrated superior adaptation processes, leading to a reduced risk of a low Apgar score (within the range of 1-3 points).

3. Neonates with elevated levels of C-reactive protein displayed more pronounced respiratory issues and necessitated twice as many instances of administering surfactant preparations, respiratory support through n-CPAP therapy, and mechanical ventilation of the lungs, suggesting the emergence of a subgroup of patients exhibiting characteristics of "severe" sepsis.

References

- Henry CJ, Semova G, Barnes E, et al. Neonatal sepsis: a systematic review of core outcomes from randomised clinical trials. *Pediatric Research*. 2022; 91. c. 735 – 42.
- Celik IH, Hanna M, Canpolat FE. Diagnosis of Neonatal Sepsis: The Past, Present and Future. *Pediatr Res*. 2022; 91(2):337–50.
- Bezrukov L.O., Koloskova O.K., Vlasova O.V. Diagnostic value parameters of acute phase reactances of infections-inflammatory process in

diagnostics of early neonatal sepsis «EUREKA: Health Sciences». 2018;5:20-27.

4. Власова О.В., Безруков Л.О., Колоскова О.К. Клініко-епідеміологічний аналіз материнських чинників схильності до неонатального сепсису за умов різного екологічного впливу. *Современная педиатрия*. 2019;100(4):33-37.

5. Newman TB, Ruopolo KM, Wi S, Draper D, Escobar GJ. Interpreting complete blood counts soon after birth in newborn at risk for sepsis. *Pediatrics*. 2010;126(5):903-9. doi: [10.1542/peds.2010-0935](https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2010-0935)

6. Павлушкина ЛВ, Филатова НФ, Черневская ЕА, Дмитриева ИБ, Белобородова НВ. Биомаркеры в клинической практике. *Лаборатория*. 2013;3(Спецвып):10-4.

7. Poggi C, Bianconi T, Gozzini E, Generoso M, Dani C. Presepsin for the detection of late-onset sepsis in preterm newborns. *Pediatrics*. 2015;135(1):68-75. doi: [10.1542/peds.2014-1755](https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2014-1755)

8. Tziialla C, Manzoni P, Achille C, Bollani L, Stronati M, Borghesi A. New Diagnostic Possibilities for Neonatal Sepsis. *Am J Perinatol* [Internet]. 2018[cited 2018 Dec 17];35(6):575-7. Available from: <https://www.thieme-connect.com/products/ejournals/abstract/10.1055/s-0038-1639361> doi: [10.1055/s-0038-1639361](https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0038-1639361)

9. Неонатологія. Навчальний посібник. За ред. Т.К. Знаменської. Київ, 2021. С. 338-352.

10. Sarafidis K. Special Issue "Recent Advances in Neonatal Sepsis". *Journal of Clinical Medicine*. 2023; 12(4):1385. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm12041385>

11. Wong HR. Pediatric sepsis biomarkers for prognostic and predictive enrichment. *Pediatr. Res*. 2021;91:283–8

12. Костюк О.О., Шунько Є.Є., Краснова Ю.Ю. Ранній неонатальний сепсис. Основні напрямки діагностики та лікування / Неонатологія, хірургія та перинатальна медицина. – Т.4, №3 (13). – 2014. – С. 110-115.

13. But Š, Celr B, Fister P. Tackling Neonatal Sepsis—Can It Be Predicted? *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. 2023; 20(4):3644. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20043644>

14. Мавропуло Т.В. Пізній неонатальний сепсис / *Інфекція*. - №1(63). 2018. – С.31-35.